

A heuristic for fitting piecewise-linear models of bivariate functions with simplices and its application to an industrial use case.*

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Abstract. A common approach to solving MINLP problems is to convert them to a MILP using piecewise-linear (PWL) models to approximate the nonlinearities. However, finding a PWL approximation that respects an error tolerance with the minimum number of linear pieces is a challenging task. Moreover, available methods are complicated and difficult to implement. This paper addresses finding error-bounded PWL approximations for continuous and smooth bivariate functions. The method proposed is an easy-to-implement heuristic applied for the case of a triangulation generated over rectangular grids. On each iteration, a nonlinear programming problem is solved to adjust the placement of the linear pieces to minimize the approximation error. Then, we increase the number of breakpoints for the variable with maximum error reduction potential. For an industrial use case from the steelmaking industry, we show how applying this heuristic can reduce the complexity of the resulting MILP while respecting a strict approximation error requirement. The heuristic achieved an average reduction of 67% in the solution time of the MILP with an average 34% reduction in the approximation error.

Keywords: Piecewise linear approximation · Global optimization · Mixed-integer linear programming · Steelmaking

1 Introduction

Mixed-integer nonlinear programming (MINLP) problems arise for several industrial applications [12]. They are usually found in problems where one needs to accurately model physical phenomena, such as chemical reactions, energy balances, and material flows through a facility [7]. A common approach to globally

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solve MINLPs is to approximate the nonlinearities by piecewise linear (PWL) functions to obtain a mixed-integer linear programming (MILP) problem that can be solved efficiently with robust methods [3].

Addressing how to best implement PWL functions in MILPs has been extensively investigated [13]. However, more effort is still required to determine a PWL approximation that results in a tractable MILP. This entails finding a PWL approximation that respects an error tolerance with the minimum number of linear pieces [6]. Different methods have been investigated in the literature for this task. Heuristics and exact methods have been developed for univariate functions [1,9]. The application to multivariate functions by partitioning the domain into convex polytopes has been addressed by [11,6,2]. The interest of this paper is in methods for continuous bivariate functions partitioned over triangles. To our knowledge, this was mainly addressed by Rebennack and Kallrath [8]. They proposed a heuristic to partition the domain into triangles until a desired error bound is achieved by linear functions fitted to each one. Then, a complex nonlinear programming (NLP) problem needs to be solved for each iteration.

Implementing the methods available in the literature requires considerable effort. Hence, our main contribution is to propose an easy-to-implement heuristic to obtain error-bounded approximations based on a rectangular grid. We use a greedy approach to increase the variable's number of breakpoints with the maximum error reduction potential on each iteration. This is executed after an NLP problem is solved to find the optimal location of the vertices of the triangles from a J1 triangulation. We do not expect it to provide the best PWL approximation. Our ultimate goal is to provide practitioners with a quick method to reduce the burden of constructing an adequate PWL approximation, enabling them to focus on the optimization problem. In addition, its compatibility with the logarithmic representation provides the highest performance during the MILP solution [13].

We applied the proposed heuristic to the ladle dispatching with refractory temperature control problem [10]. It can achieve a strict approximation error with few breakpoints. This enabled us to reduce the amount of binary and continuous variables required with a better approximation error. Hence, this led to a significant decrease in the computation time needed to reach optimality compared to the previously employed equidistant grid. It shows the potential of the heuristic for a complex optimization problem.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the general grid fitting problem under consideration. Section 3 describes the PWL fitting heuristic developed. Section 4 briefly introduces the industrial use case and then evaluates the results of applying the proposed heuristic. Finally, Section 5 summarizes the findings and discusses the next steps.

2 Problem statement

Consider a finite set of m data points $D : (\mathbf{x}_i, y_i) \in \mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}, i \in [1, \dots, m]$ sampled from a bivariate nonlinear function. Our problem consists of finding a set of continuous PWL functions F over a domain \mathcal{P} that contains all \mathbf{x}_i . This

can be written as a fitting problem of the form [11]:

$$\begin{aligned} \min \max \{ & | f(\mathbf{x}_i) - y_i | : \forall i \in [1, \dots, m] \} \\ \text{s.t. } & f \in F \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Solving this problem yields a continuous PWL function f that best fits the data set according to the maximum norm. For this paper, we restrict our function f to be generated over a pre-defined triangulation S from a rectangular grid. Several approaches exist to construct a valid triangulation, but we focus on the J1 type (or “Union Jack”) as it is key to achieving good MILP performance with the logarithmic coding. In fact, this approach is by orders of magnitude faster on even moderately detailed models [13]. Since a rectangular grid is defined over an ordered set of breakpoints per dimension, their optimal placement is the solution of Problem 1.

Increasing the number of breakpoints is the easiest way to minimize the approximation error, but it can easily lead to intractable MILPs [3]. Hence, we are also interested in finding a function f with the minimum number of triangles. A rectangular grid achieves non-overlapping triangles with continuity in the vertices by enforcing them to be at regular positions. By not considering irregular triangulations, we can expect the final number of triangles to be higher than the ideal optimum.

3 Piecewise linear fitting heuristic

The proposed heuristic for bivariate functions is summarized in Algorithm 1. A given data set D must be provided to evaluate the quality of the PWL fitting. We require the data to adequately represent the behavior of the nonlinear function in its entire domain \mathcal{P} . It is recommended to avoid too many points to limit the time taken to evaluate the error metric. Furthermore, a maximum number of breakpoints per variable $b_{\max} \in \mathbb{N}$ and an approximation error tolerance $\delta^{\max} \in \mathbb{R}^+$ must be specified as termination criteria. Until convergence, the algorithm alternates between the solution of Problem 1 and the adjustment of the number of breakpoints. The final result is the number of breakpoints $n_1, n_2 \in \mathbb{N}$ and their optimal locations $\mathbf{b}_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{n_1}$ and $\mathbf{b}_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{n_2}$ that minimize the fitting error metric. Each step is described in detail in the following sections.

3.1 Rectangular Grid Fitting

Let $S(\mathbf{b}_1, \mathbf{b}_2)$ be a J1 triangulation constructed over the rectangular grid defined by $\mathbf{b}_1, \mathbf{b}_2$. Given that the elements of \mathbf{b}_1 and \mathbf{b}_2 are unique and in ascending order, optimizing the location of the breakpoints can be done by solving the following optimization problem:

Algorithm 1: Piecewise linear fitting heuristic

Data: the evaluation data set D , select n_1^0 and n_2^0 breakpoints, b_{\max} , δ^{\max}
Result: the new breakpoints n_1^* , n_2^* and their location \mathbf{b}_1^* and \mathbf{b}_2^*
 $n_{1,0} \leftarrow n_1^0$; $n_{2,0} \leftarrow n_2^0$; $\delta_0 \leftarrow \infty$; $t \leftarrow 1$;
Solve the **Rectangular Grid Fitting** to obtain $\mathbf{b}_{1,t}$, $\mathbf{b}_{2,t}$ and δ_t
while ($n_{1,t-1} \leq b_{\max}$ or $n_{2,t-1} \leq b_{\max}$) and $\delta_{t-1} \geq \delta^{\max}$ **do**
 Execute the **Grid Size Adjustment Sub-Algorithm** to obtain $n_{1,t}$, $n_{2,t}$
 Solve the **Rectangular Grid Fitting** to obtain $\mathbf{b}_{1,t}$, $\mathbf{b}_{2,t}$ and δ_t
 $t \leftarrow t + 1$
end
 $n_1^* \leftarrow n_{1,t-1}$; $n_2^* \leftarrow n_{2,t-1}$; $\mathbf{b}_1^* \leftarrow \mathbf{b}_{1,t-1}$; $\mathbf{b}_2^* \leftarrow \mathbf{b}_{2,t-1}$;

$$\min_{\mathbf{b}_1, \mathbf{b}_2} \max\{|f(\mathbf{x}_i) - y_i| : \forall i \in [1, \dots, m]\}$$

$$s.t. \quad \mathbf{b}_{d,1} = \mathbf{b}_d^{\min}, \forall d \in [1, 2] \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{b}_{d,n_d} = \mathbf{b}_d^{\max}, \forall d \in [1, 2] \quad (3)$$

$$\mathbf{b}_{d,j} \geq \mathbf{b}_{d,j-1} + \epsilon, \forall d \in [1, 2], \forall j \in [2, \dots, n_d] \quad (4)$$

$$f \in S(\mathbf{b}_1, \mathbf{b}_2)$$

The minimum and maximum values of \mathbf{b}_1 and \mathbf{b}_2 are fixed and coincide with the bounds of the function domain, which we name $\mathbf{b}^{\min} \in \mathbb{R}^2$ and $\mathbf{b}^{\max} \in \mathbb{R}^2$ respectively. Hence, Constraints 2 and 3 enforce each variable's first and last breakpoints to match precisely the domain bounds. Constraints 4 ensure that the breakpoints are in order. A positive offset $\epsilon \in \mathbb{R}^+$ prevents breakpoints at the same position. This yields an NLP problem that can be solved with any constrained solver.

The biggest bottleneck is the evaluation of the objective function. Each candidate solution requires constructing a new triangulation and then identifying the simplex to which each evaluation point \mathbf{x}_i belongs. In the worst case, we must evaluate all the simplices from S . Hence, the complexity of this problem is significantly affected by the number of breakpoints [11]. Therefore, we used a nearest-neighbors lookup based on the geometric center of the simplices to reduce the number of simplices evaluated. Finally, we can estimate $f(\mathbf{x}_i)$ as the convex combination of the vertices of the active simplex [13].

3.2 Grid Size Adjustment Sub-Algorithm

If the error threshold cannot be achieved with optimally fitted breakpoints, we need to increase the granularity of the rectangular grid. Hence, we propose a greedy heuristic to increase the breakpoints in a forward fashion. This is described in Algorithm 2. Initially, we check if the number of breakpoints is reached for any variable. In this situation, the only possible action is to increase the number of breakpoints of the variable for which this is allowed.

Otherwise, we first calculate the absolute error of each point in D over the previously fitted PWL function f . Then, we choose the point with the maximum absolute error, \mathbf{x}^{\max} , to determine how to increase the breakpoints. Refining the grid near this point will lead to the highest decrease in the overall approximation error. Hence, for each dimension at a time, we add two breakpoints at equidistant locations to the line segment \bar{L}_{\max} that contains \mathbf{x}^{\max} . Adding two points is important to ensure the new triangulation obtained is comparable to the original one. Using this approach, we estimate the maximum absolute error σ over D for each dimension.

We then choose to increase the dimension with the minimum σ , which can maximize the potential decrease in the overall approximation error. Since we are interested in keeping the number of breakpoints as low as possible, we only increase the breakpoints by one per iteration. To speed up the convergence of the grid-fitting algorithm for the next iteration, we can provide a good initial solution by placing the new breakpoint at the midpoint of \bar{L}_{\max} . Placing it exactly at \mathbf{x}^{\max} or using an equidistant grid are also viable alternatives and can be further evaluated in future works.

Algorithm 2: Grid Size Adjustment Sub-Algorithm

Data: The PWL function f and the number breakpoints $n_{1,t-1}, n_{2,t-1}$
Result: The new number of breakpoints $n_{1,t}, n_{2,t}$
 $r_1 \leftarrow 0; r_2 \leftarrow 0; \sigma \leftarrow \emptyset;$
for $k = 1$ **to** 2 **do**
 if $n_{k,t-1} = b_{\max}$ **then**
 $r_k \leftarrow 1; n_{k,t} = b_{\max}$
 end
end
if $r_1 = 1$ **or** $r_2 = 1$ **then**
 if $r_1 = 1$ **then**
 $n_{2,t} \leftarrow n_{2,t-1} + 1$
 else
 $n_{1,t} \leftarrow n_{1,t-1} + 1$
 end
else
 Determine the point \mathbf{x}^{\max} with maximum absolute error over f
 for $k = 1$ **to** 2 **do**
 Add two points to segment \bar{L}_{\max} containing \mathbf{x}^{\max} to determine $\mathbf{b}_k^{\text{new}}$
 $f_k \leftarrow S(\mathbf{b}_k^{\text{new}}, \cdot); \sigma_k \leftarrow \max\{|f_k(\mathbf{x}_i) - y_i| : \forall i \in [1, \dots, m]\}$
 end
 $k_{\min} \leftarrow \arg \min(\sigma);$
 $n_{k_{\min},t} \leftarrow n_{k_{\min},t-1} + 1; n_{k,t} \leftarrow n_{k,t-1}, \forall k \in [1, 2] \setminus k_{\min}$
end

4 Industrial use case

Ruela et al. [10] proposed a MILP model of the ladle dispatching problem with the thermal balance of the steel ladles. PWL models over equidistant rectangular grids were employed to approximate the ladle’s nonlinear thermal behavior. Moreover, logarithmic coding was used for the MILP representation. In this problem, a high-fidelity linear approximation is paramount to prevent the error from propagating between ladle cycles and compromising the final optimal solution. This can be achieved by increasing the number of breakpoints. However, it may lead to intractable problems due to the high number of linear pieces. Hence, employing the proposed heuristic is expected to reduce the computation burden while respecting strict approximation error requirements.

4.1 Experimental results

We applied the proposed heuristic to the nonlinear refractory temperature models considering D a rectangular grid with 50 equidistant breakpoints per dimension to evaluate the approximation error. Moreover, 20 neighbors were empirically considered ideal for the simplex lookup operation. The initial number of breakpoints is $n_1^0 = n_2^0 = 3$ and $b_{\max} = 12$. A tolerance $\epsilon = 0.001$ was used for Constraints 4. The heuristic is implemented in Python 3.10 and uses the Differential Evolution (DE) algorithm from SciPy with the default parameters to solve the grid fitting step to avoid premature convergence. All experiments were executed on a 128-core system (AMD EPYC 7702P) with 256GB RAM. ¹

Table 1: Summary of computational results

	Baseline			Target-Baseline			Target-10				
Stage	n_1	n_2	δ	n_1	n_2	δ	Time (s)	n_1	n_2	δ	Time (s)
Empty	12	12	17.23	4	6	15.01	3608	5	7	9.94	11029
Heating	12	12	54.52	6	4	35.62	3143	6	8	8.21	19937
Casting	12	12	14.06	7	7	11.93	20409	7	8	9.73	32162
Full	12	12	39.41	7	5	23.11	7387	5	10	9.85	16900

The results of applying the proposed heuristic for three different configurations are displayed in Table 1. The **Baseline** is an equidistant grid with 12 breakpoints per dimension [10]. **Target-Baseline** applies the heuristic to achieve the same approximation error of the baseline over D . We also evaluate a strict error target of $\delta_{\max} = 10$, referred to as **Target-10**. Table 1 shows that the heuristic significantly reduced the number of breakpoints while keeping the maximum absolute error within the specified error bounds. It highlights how important it

¹ The source code and relevant data are available at <https://gitlab.tuwien.ac.at/iet/public/pwl-heuristic-cesaref>

is to choose the location of the breakpoints to obtain adequate approximations with a rectangular grid. However, a long convergence time can be required under a strict error bound. Therefore, the proposed heuristic is more suitable for problems where the function domain bounds are not changed often. Figure 1 displays the final approximation obtained with Target-10. Notice that the error threshold is respected in the entire function domain.

Fig. 1: The approximation error for configuration Target-10 for each ladle operation. The boundaries of the simplices are highlighted in white.

We now evaluate the effect of applying the grid fitted from Target-Baseline and Target-10 to solve the ladle dispatching problem. The optimization problem was implemented in Python 3.10 with Pyomo 6.5.0 modeling language [5], and we used Gurobi 10.0.0 [4] as the solver. We allowed a maximum runtime of 10000 seconds or a 0.1% optimality gap. We consider three different representative production scenarios, each with a refractory temperature constraint of 700 °C. Ladles are new (0 lifetime) and have an initial temperature of 700 °C. A comparison of the results is displayed in Table 2. BV and CV stand for binary and continuous variables, respectively. Here, δ is calculated as the maximum absolute error between the PWL model predictions and nonlinear models for the optimal solution obtained.

The results show that the heuristic significantly reduced the time required to reach the optimality gap for all scenarios. For scenario 1, the Baseline achieved an optimality gap of 1.38% in the specified time limit. This is a direct result of reducing the number of binary and continuous variables. Moreover, Target-

Table 2: Computational results of heuristic applied to selected instances of the ladle dispatching problem.

Scenario	Configuration	BV	CV	δ	Time (s)	Objective
1	Baseline	2509	18347	32.72	10000	1440
	Target-Baseline	2215	6209	29.04	967	1431
	Target-10	2236	7448	17.96	1205	1421
2	Baseline	4096	22268	23.4	2026	947
	Target-Baseline	3760	8396	25.3	716	949
	Target-10	3784	9812	13.07	525	940
3	Baseline	3235	22089	26.49	2416	1567
	Target-Baseline	2885	7639	22.88	1278	1568
	Target-10	2910	9114	22.93	1417	1560

Baseline required less computational effort for scenarios 1 and 3 but resulted in a lower reduction of the approximation error. This is likely an effect of the error propagation between ladle cycles, which also caused minor deviations in the objective value. Finally, Target-10 achieved the best balance between solution time and approximation error for all the instances evaluated. For example, it reduced them on average by 67% and 34%, respectively. Hence, such improvement can unlock solving representative instances efficiently without compromising the approximation accuracy.

5 Conclusion

This paper presented a heuristic to compute PWL approximations for a J1 triangulation constructed over a rectangular grid that satisfies a given error threshold for a reference data set with few triangles. The proposed heuristic was applied to a complex industrial use case [10]. We showed it could generate accurate approximations with fewer continuous and binary variables. This was achieved with a lower approximation error and reduced runtime. Hence, it shows the effectiveness of the proposed heuristic and how it can improve the performance of applications with rigorous approximation quality requirements.

The results showed an essential step towards improving the solution of the use case under consideration. However, we can identify some directions for improving the heuristic. First, it can require considerable time to converge with a global solver and hinder its application when the function domain is changed very often. Given DE’s stochastic nature, different solutions can be obtained for each execution. Hence, future works can explore exact solvers to address both limitations. Besides, being able to approximate models with more than three variables is still an open problem. Investigating machine learning methods to obtain optimal PWL functions and integrate them efficiently in a MILP is a good research direction and can significantly benefit practitioners.

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